

Alternative to Hormone Therapy for Reproductive Infringements in Girls-Teenagers

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Abstract: The problem of girls' reproductive health and their reproductive potential as expectant mothers attracts close attention of scientific researchers, since along with medical significance, it is increasingly gaining social significance. Negative trends in the medical and demographic situation (increasing morbidity of the population, environmental stresses) strongly dictate that special attention should be paid to the reproductive health of the younger generation [1,2]. The frequency of disorders in the development of the reproductive system and deviations in the psychosomatic health of adolescents has increased.

Keywords: girls-teenagers, reproductive infringements, sexual development.

Introduction: The problem of reproductive health of girls-teenagers in the modern world remains one of the most urgent and interdisciplinary, since the medical and demographic situation continues to be unfavorable and the health of women of fertile age is deteriorating

The researchers' opinion boils down to the fact that the course of puberty largely depends on both the somatic status of a teenager and the psycho-emotional changes that accompany this age stage. (3,4,5) An indisputable fact is the determining value of the premorbid background in the formation of many systems and functions of the body. Puberty is also affected by both endogenous and exogenous factors, which are often interrelated. (6,7,8)

Determination of the clinical and pathogenetic patterns of the appearance and development of reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers made it possible to differentially choose an individual examination scheme and a modified treatment regimen, which facilitated successful treatment in 74% of cases. The results of the conducted therapeutic measures confirm the expediency of active management of girls-teenagers with reproductive infringements using modern drug technologies.

Purpose of the study: to study the characteristics of reproductive disorders in the modern population of teenage girls, to determine criteria for early diagnosis and monitoring the effectiveness of treatment.

Materials and methods of research: 78 teenage girls with reproductive disorders of varying degrees. An objective assessment of sexual development, ultrasound, x-ray, and hormonal studies were carried out.

Results of our own research: we examined 78 teenage girls with reproductive disorders

Group 1 consisted of 36 girls with impaired sexual development, but maintaining normal menstrual function;

Group 2 – 42 girls with menstrual irregularities against the background of normal sexual development;

They underwent clinical (anamnestic data), instrumental (ultrasound), hormonal (content of follicle-stimulating hormone, LH-luteinizing hormone, estradiol, free testosterone in blood serum) tests.

A comparative description of menstrual function disorders in the examined patients showed that the timely onset of a regular cycle (12.5-13 years) was observed in 80% of patients of group 1, the formation of menstrual function took about 6 months in 24, only 12 had a later formation.

Patients with severe menstrual disorders (group 2) are characterized by earlier menarche in 32 (76%) or later – in 10 (24%), while long – term development of the menstrual cycle-in 13 (30.9%). Group 2 patients were characterized by a high frequency of irregular menstrual cycle in 29 (69%) patients, accompanied by severe pain syndrome in 28 (66.7%). These deviations were more pronounced in patients of group 2, where there was a clear negative tendency to desynchronization and led to a violation of the menstrual cycle in them.

It is necessary to note the fact of a mutual combination of extragenital diseases in one patient with an element of mutual burden, which resulted in hormonal disorders that developed later.

Further comparison of clinical and anamnestic data of somatic and gynecological health showed its burden with various gynecological diseases, where a high frequency of gynecological diseases of inflammatory genesis (vulvovaginitis, adnexitis) was observed in patients of all compared groups, which could not but affect the formation of reproductive health of girls-teenagers in the future.

Consequently, the results of the analysis of the formation of menstrual function in girls-teenagers showed a longer period of formation of reciprocal relationships in the HGNAS with the development of reproductive pathology. At the same time, the menstrual cycle did not always remain regular.

Correction of the revealed disorders was carried out taking into account the hormonal activity of the ovaries in comparison with the gonadotropic activity of the hypothalamic-pituitary system.

In addition, taking into account the delicacy of age, hormone phobia of parents and then teenagers, their lack of discipline in adhering to the treatment regimen, we considered it justified to prescribe to the examined group of patients a herbal medicine drug that has a hormone-like (estrogen-like) effect - Klimadynon (Germany) in combination with anti-inflammatory, restorative, immunomodulatory drugs. The method of determining the effectiveness of treatment was to compare the clinical (subjective) and instrumental – laboratory (objective) data in the dynamics of observation.

In order to optimize the management tactics of girls-teenagers with reproductive infringements, we used the herbal medicine Klimadynon in combination with complex treatment. The therapeutic efficacy of Klimadynon is evident in patients with isolated reproductive infringements of 80.5% and 78.6%, respectively, in groups 1 and 2.

Comparison of the results of treatment with Klimadynon in patients with different reproductive infringements indicates a similar effect on the state of the reproductive system: there was synchronization in the development of secondary sexual characteristics, ultrasound parameters of the uterus and appendages improved, signs of the inflammatory process of the genitals disappeared, and the hormonal profile normalized (functional diagnostics tests, radioimmune hormone analysis).

Taking into account the high frequency of multisystem disorders that contribute to the development of reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers, the complex of therapeutic measures included medicines that improve the functional state of the organs and systems involved in the pathological process: general strengthening, anti-inflammatory, anti-anemic and other drugs.

Attention is drawn to the faster onset of the therapeutic effect in patients of group 1 (2-3 months), while in patients of group 2 the treatment went at a slower pace (4-6 months).

Thus, we have proved the high efficiency of treatment of reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers using the drug Klimadynon (74%), which is the reason for its inclusion in the treatment regimen of this cohort of patients.

Results obtained: The frequency of reproductive infringements in the screening examination of girls-teenagers was clarified. The role of somatic status and clinical manifestations of reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers was studied. A management scheme for girls-teenagers with various reproductive infringements, depending on their origin, has been developed and implemented.

Conclusions: Thus, when detecting reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers, corrective treatment should be comprehensive and should be carried out taking into account the severity of reproductive infringements that contribute to gynecological and extragenital pathology. It is advisable to use a treatment regimen that includes parallel administration of anti-inflammatory, general strengthening (cyclic vitamin therapy), anti-anemic (iron preparations) and herbal medicine.

The duration of herbal medicine with Klimadynon (3 months, 1 tablet 2 times a day) proportionally depends on the severity of reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers and its effectiveness is determined by the duration of drug administration regimens, as well as the patient's age.

The selected risk groups made it possible to carry out therapeutic and preventive measures aimed at timely correction of violations, strengthening medical alertness to the implementation of genetically "programmed" risk factors. Determination of the clinical and pathogenetic patterns of the appearance and development of reproductive infringements in girls-teenagers made it possible to differentially choose an individual scheme of examination and treatment.

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